

Effects of Work-Life Balance on Health and Wellbeing of Employees in the Nigeria Banking Industry

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between work-life balance and employee health and wellbeing in the Nigerian banking industry. The study was based exclusively on primary data obtained by administering a well-structured questionnaire and conducted at the headquarters of the banks located in the state of Lagos. The random sampling technique used to select banks and bank employees was deliberately selected because they are the focus of the study. Yamane's formula was used to determine the sample size of 50 employees.

The multiple regression analysis showed that all the stated predictors significantly affected employee's health and wellbeing in the Nigerian banking industry, where $R^2 = 0.996$, $F(4, 45) = 2590.451$, $P < 0.01$. Thus, there is a significant relationship between work-life balance and employee health and wellbeing in the Nigerian banking industry. The study, therefore, recommends that there is a need for the banking sector and corporate bodies in Nigeria to improve the working conditions of employees. Also, the negative relationship from welfare facilities suggests a state of neglect on the part of management; thus, more attention needs to be given to the welfare package of newly recruited employees in the Nigerian banking industry.

Keywords: Employee's Well-Being, Compensation, Health, Work-Life-Balance, Remuneration and Work-Family-Conflict

INTRODUCTION

Work is part of life, and in today's work environment, people generally faced with a lot of difficulties in balancing their work and family life. To achieve tasks and a balanced-life efficiently, the policies to employ depend on both the employees and employers. Research has shown that both employees and organizations benefit from successful balanced work and family life (Greenhaus and Powell, 2006; Hammer et al., 2005). In family domains, people face a lack of balance between work and life. This experience threatens critical areas of their personal lives (Lachman and Boone-James, 1997); On the other hand, the balance between work and private life improves employee health and well-being and family happiness (Grzywacz, 2000). In the work sectors, the lack of work-life balance reduces performance and increases employee absenteeism (Frone, Yardley & Markel, 1997). However, stable work and family life are associated with greater professional satisfaction.

Work-life balance means bringing work, whether done on the job or at home, and leisure time into balance to live life to its fullest. Work-life balance helps personnel keep evenness in their works and also their individual lives. The WHO (1948; 2000) definition links health explicitly with wellbeing, and conceptualises health as a

human right requiring physical and social resources to achieve and maintain. An employee who attain a work-life balance that suits them, are content and dedicated to their employer and will be efficient in their work which will yield higher productivity for the organization. Work-life balance is a combination of relations among different parts of one's life; the benefits and disadvantages associated with that balance or imbalance can affect numerous levels of society.

The key reason for encouraging work-life balance is to provide an equilibrium state for both sides (employees and employers). When there is a balance between work-life and private life pressure is reduce, while general satisfaction improves employee's quality of life, thereby increasing the efficiency of work. The weaknesses associated with work-life balance can affect both employee and employer. For the employee, a work-life imbalance can have an unfortunate consequence on their work and life satisfaction, mental health, physical health, and individual performance in an organization (Guest, 2002). For employers, the consequences of poor work-life balance will be a poor performance which will lead to reduced productivity, absenteeism, sick leave, and higher staff turnover, staffing and training costs

Work-life balance from the employee perspective is the maintenance of stability between duties at work and home. Employers are to help the employees balance their family and work domains as work-life benefits (Russell & Bowman, 2000). Both employees and employers in the organization are faced with more conflict between work and personal life as they endure to pursue the quality of life that they need (Casper et al., 2011). The use of work-life balance practices helps to reduce conflicts between work and personal life and increases the positive evaluation of the employees of the organization (Lazar, Osoian & Ratiu, 2010). Working life programs help improve the organization's

analytical, structural and cultural support for work and family (Kossek, Lewis and Hammer, 2010), while effective communication and supportive environment are the initiatives for success factors of wellbeing at work (Baicker, Cutler & Song 2010).

Thus, one of the major problems facing the current individual workers in this era is to balance work and family life successfully (Halpern, 2005). To achieve good life quality and a harmonious balance between work, individual responsibilities and interests, one needs good work-life balance.

The Importance of work-family balance, whether implicit or explicit, to the organizations and employees, cannot be overlooked. A literature review, questions this supposed link between work-life balance practices and organizational effectiveness. The tools with which the provision of working life practices affect both employee behaviour and employee productivity are not clear or investigated (Allen, 2001; Beauregard & Henry, 2009).

This study is, therefore, aimed at investigating the work-life practices in the Nigerian banking industry. It attempts to gain a better understanding of the experiences and expectations of employees in an attempt to identify the source of the work-life balance and its effect on employee health and wellbeing. Therefore, there arose the question of what are the implications of work-life balance on employee health and wellbeing in the Nigerian banking industry?

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant relationship between work-life balance and employee's health and wellbeing in the Nigerian banking industry.

The study hopes to contribute to the existing body of literatures. In addition, the study focused on work-life balance and general employee health and wellbeing, in order to provide empirical evidence to bolster the importance of work-life balance in the 21st-century work-place. Results from

this study will enable policymakers to pay more attention to the employees' health and wellbeing.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Conceptual Review

How an organisation will perform and increase its productivity is determined by the employees in such an organisation. The performances can be work-related, personal or family-related. It is pertinent to mention that how an individual copes with all aspects of life will determine how work-life balance can be achieved both at the work-place and at home, however, most of the time allocated to an individual is spent at work. Both the work-life and private life of an employee is very much essential and should be maintained. In order not to have any issues either at work or individual life, employer demands for empowered, competent and multi-tasking skilled employees to ensure the maximum growth of the organisation. An employee who works in this era experienced the problem of performing adequately well and is forced to dedicate most of their time to their working place.

However, to fulfil the demand and duty of the work-place, individual employees must be committed to their self-development, loyalty to their family and social life; these are essential ingredients that every member of an organisation must adhere to. The importance of the work-life balance of employees is the variables that influence work-life balance in modern work and life settings and in this era cannot be overemphasised.

Work-Life Balance

The term work-life balance is commonly used as a more complete expression to describe policies that have been classified as "family friends", which are an extension that is beyond the reach of the family. Work-life balance refers to the flexible working arrangement that allows both parents and non-parent to avail of working methods that prove a balance

between work responsibilities and personal responsibilities. In practice, it involves adapting work patterns so that everyone, regardless of age, race or gender, can find a space that allows them to easily combine work with other responsibilities and aspirations (Pillinger, 2001). It points out that personal fulfilment is essential inside work and that satisfaction outside work may enhance employee's contribution to work.

Work-life balance is a concept that includes the correct definition of priorities between "work" (career and ambition) and "lifestyle" (health, pleasure, family leisure and spiritual development / meditation). They were related, albeit in broader terms, to include "calm lifestyle balance" and lifestyle choices. "The work-leisure dichotomy was invented in the mid-1800s. Krassner (2014) commented that anthropologists use a definition of happiness which means having as little separation as possible "between your work and your game". The expression "work-life balance (WLB)" was first used in the UK in the late 1970s and in the United States in 1986 to describe the balance between individual work and personal life (Kossek, 2006).

Measuring Work-Life Balance

Work-life measurement is a component critical for mapping out the work environment in any organisation that recognised it as an essential tool for any researcher. Work-life balance can be evaluated in terms of work-family conflict, which is in line with the representation made by Greenhaus and Beutell (1985), this includes different types of disputes such as strain-based conflicts which exist when psychologically produced within a role, affects the other functioning individual role. Strain based conflicts are intense on the employee's base on physical, emotional or mental work demand. Behaviour-based battles which comprise of four dimensions to measure work-life-family strains and gains among working couples

B. Theoretical Review

Several theories have suggested clarifying the concept of Work-Life Balance. These include Border, Spill over and Compensation theory and enrichment theory.

The Boarder theory has to do with private lives and work circles. It stresses the point that individuals are everyday border crossers as they advanced among work and family. According to the theory, the flexibility and permeability of the boundaries between people's work and family life will influence the level of integration, the ease of transitions and the level of conflict between these domains. Flexible and permeable borders facilitate integration between work and home domains. When areas are relatively integrated, the transition is more comfortable, but work-family conflict is more likely. Conversely, when these domains are segmented, a change is more difficult, but family-work conflict is less likely (Bellavia & Frone, 2005).

Clark (2000), in his study, suggested that the purpose of border theory is all about supporting performance and working effectively both at home and work-place.

Guest (2002) proposed the spillover theory and claimed that the conditions under which overflow can occur are between work and family. He noted that this could either be negative or positive. Spill over theory proposes that if work and family influences are meticulously planned within period and space, then spill over in terms of conduct, time and energy will be negative. The category of work-life balance, as explained, has been both an objective and subjective way. The purpose pointers include a period of work and hours of devoted or permitted time outside work. Individual indicators denote the state of balance and imbalance. He also noted that balance is described as when equivalent importance is sure to both work and home or when home or work controls by choice. Likewise, when there is an elasticity that allows an individual to partake and link household together with

work obligations, this will bring about positive spill over that is influential to understanding a proper and well work-life balance. Overflow consequently occurs once there is the interference of one stage of life into another. The importance of these theories to the study is that organisation is probable to embrace positive work-life balance practices which will make every employee more devoted towards achieving higher productivity.

Compensation theory proposed that workers try to compensate for the lack of satisfaction in one sector (work or home) by trying to find more pleasure in the other (Lambert, 1990). Piotrkowski (1979) also concluded that men "see their homes as shelters, see their families as sources of satisfaction lacking in the occupational sphere". Two forms of compensation have been identified in the literature (Edwards & Rothbard, 2000). First, a person can decrease participation in the unsatisfactory sector and increase participation in a potentially satisfactory area (Lambert, 1990). Second, the person may respond to dissatisfaction in one field by pursuing rewards in the other domain (Champoux, 1978).

According to enrichment theory, experience in one role, either work or family, will enhance the quality of life in the other character. Nevertheless, the model in question tries to explain the positive effects of the work-family relationship. This theory of enrichment refers to the degree to which experiences from instrumental sources (skills, abilities, values) or useful sources (mood, satisfaction) improve the quality of the other domain (Morris & Madsen, 2007). Greenhaus & Powell (2006) defined enrichment as "the extent to which experiences in one role improve the quality of life in the other role" and reported that employees perceive that their job and life roles are enriched at each other. Zedeck & Mosier (1990) used the instrumental term to describe this notion, which states that such good results in the workplace lead to good results in personal life and vice versa.

C. Empirical Review

There are several studies carried out that supported the effect of work-life balance on employee health and wellbeing, for example Arunika & Kottawatta (2015) considered work-life balance on employee job performance - among non-executive in the public banking sector in Colombia. The study applies Univariate, Bivariate and Multivariate methods to analyse the effect of work-life on employee job performance as well as among non-executive in the public banking sector. The outcomes point out that the relationship between work-life balance and employee satisfaction is negative. It concludes that in order to reduce the work-life conflict of non-Executives, the bank management has to introduce various incentives in order to get a maximum contribution from the employees.

Darko-Asumadu, Sika-Bright & Osei-Tutu (2018) conducted a study on the influence of work-life balance on employee's commitment among bankers in Accra Ghana, using Descriptive cross-sectional survey. This result confirms that the relationship between employee commitment and their work-life balance has a weak positive effect on employees because they are not satisfied with study leave, part-time work, and paternity leave. It also concludes that the policy of work-life balance does not have an influence on individual workers in the bank. The research recommended that workers should enjoy study leave, part-time work, and paternity leave to enhance work-life balance.

According to (Pathak, Dubey, & Singh, 2019), work-life balance and job satisfaction in India using past literature and secondary data find out that the study has a significant impact on the work-life balance of individual employee and influence job satisfaction of employees in the industries. It shows that the result of the survey will have an extensive influence on the work-life balance of individual employees and improve the job satisfaction of employees in the industries. The study concludes that work-life balance has a significant impact

on employee job performance, health and wellbeing.

Mendis & Weerakkody (2017) examined the impact of work-life balance on employee performance reference to telecommunication industries. The study aimed to explore the impact of work-life balance on comparative analysis of employee performance in the telecommunications sectors. The cluster sampling process was used for this study. This result shows that the relationship between work-life balance and employee performance is positive and that there is a strong relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance. This study concludes that employees that have balanced work and life tend to have higher performance and job satisfaction. It also recommends that the organization have to progress on the work-life balance of management and employees in order to increase employee job satisfaction.

D. Conceptual Framework

MATERIALS & METHODS

This study will make use of primary data. The study is being conducted in banks' headquarters located in Lagos. The choice of Lagos State was based on the fact that most head offices of Nigerian banks are in Lagos. A random sampling technique was used to select the banks, and a purposive sampling technique was used to select the bank's employees. The banks' employees were purposively selected because they are the centrepiece of the study. Yamane

formula was used to determine the sample size of 397 respondents out of the total population of 52,596. Data collected will be analyzed using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistics.

The full regression model for the study is $EMPW = \beta_0 + \beta_1HS + \beta_2WF + \beta_1WC + \beta_2CPS + \varepsilon$

Where

EMPW = Employee Wellbeing

HS = Health and Safety

WF = Welfare Facilities

WC = work Condition

CPS = Compensation

A positive relationship is expected between all the variables

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

The employee health and wellbeing was significantly predicted at $R^2 = 0.996$, $F = (4, 45) = 2590.451$, $P < 0.01$. The model explains 99.6% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.996$) in employee wellbeing.

The multiple coefficients of variation (R) of 0.998 depicted a great and positive relationship between the work-life balance and employee wellbeing. Also, the F ratio of 2590.451 was statistically

significant at the 0.01 level. The beta weights (β), showed that compensation (CPS) has the most substantial impact of (45.1%), and followed by health and safety (HS) with (38.3%). The least contribution came from working condition (WC) with (23.8%), while a negative relationship came from welfare facilities. These results are consistent with Darko-Asumadu, Sika-Bright & Osei-Tutu (2018), where the welfare facilities have the least and negative contribution in predicting employee's welfare and wellbeing by extension.

A Durbin Watson value of less than 1.5 is an indication of serial correlation. An amount higher than 1 or less than 3 is recommended (Field, 2009). The result of the Durbin Watson (DW) was satisfactory (approximately 2), indicating no autocorrelation between the residuals from the regression model. Thus, all the stated work-life balance predictors significantly affected the general employee's wellbeing in the Nigerian banking industry. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between work-life balance and employee welfare in the Nigerian banking industry.

Table1: Multiple Regression of Effect of Work-Life The balance on Employees Health and Wellbeing

Analysis of Variance					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Significance
Regression	597.406	4	149.351	2590.451	.000 ^b
Residual	2.594	45	.058		
Total	600.000	49			
Coefficients					
Independent variables	Beta	t	Significance		
HS	.383	5.540	.000		
WF	-.002	-.025	.980		
WC	.238	9.256	.000		
CPS	.451	9.537	.000		
Correlational Statistics					
Dependent variable	Multiple R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	S.E of Estimate	Durbin Watson
EMPW	.998 ^a	.996	.995	.24011	2.464

Source: Author's computation, 2020

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study provided insight into the extent of work-life balance and employee health and wellbeing in the Nigerian banking industry.

The findings revealed that all the stated variables played a significant role in

influencing the health and wellbeing of employees in the Nigerian banking industry. The identified predictors are health and safety (HS), welfare facilities (WF), work conditions (WC), and compensation (CPS). Among all the identified predictors, benefit (CPS) has the most substantial influence on employee wellbeing, followed by health and

safety (HS), and the least impact came from working conditions (WC). In contrast, a negative relationship came from welfare facilities. Therefore, there is a need for the banking sector and corporate bodies in Nigeria to improve the working conditions of their employees. Also, the negative relationship from welfare facilities suggests a state of neglect on the part of management. Thus more attention needs to be given to the welfare package of old employees and newly recruited employees in the Nigerian banking industry.

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